

Edible Cities Network – Integrating Edible City Solutions for social, resilient and sustainably productive Cities

EdiCitNet

Deliverable D6.4

Action Plan of ECS Business/Blended Consulting Team

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1. Executive Summary

The **Business Consulting Team (BCT) Action Plan** is a description of activities that are going to be undertaken by the **ECS Business Consulting Team** during the lifetime of the project. Based on the findings of several workshops¹ and discussions with **Edible City Solution Initiatives (ECSI)** and other activities and meetings the BCT is broadening their activities to so called “**blended consulting**”². This term was introduced within the EdiCitNet Consortium and in the workshops with the ECSI to reveal the intention to stabilize both ECSI working in the field of financial and social capital³. It will also be introduced to a wider scientific community.

When we talk of business consultancy in this deliverable this should mostly be understood as *blended consultancy* paying attention to the large community of ECSI working as non-profit oriented organisations that often seek public funding opportunities and subsidies within and from the City Administration. At the same time also profit-oriented ECSI, which were the main target audience in the Description of Action (DoA) were addressed. A first deep insight that has changed our understanding of ECSI’s work in the last months and underpins the experience from (informal) interactions⁴ with many ECSI and the Marketplace survey is that ECSI do not perceive themselves as being a “real” business. What these organisations need is a hybrid system⁵ of different supporting activities integrating also their need for stabilization beyond their profit and growth.

Therefore, the discussion and research on this have led to the term “blended consultancy”.

In the present deliverable we provide an overview of the role of the Business Consulting Team and the milestones included in the Action Plan. The “B” in BCT can thus stand for Business or Blended.

The Action Plan covers the internal organisation and is structuring the work of the ECS BCT. Furthermore, we provide here a conceptual and strategic plan which shows the approach to the topic of blended consulting for ECSI regarding urban re-generation and resilient cities. We also demonstrate the economic and social growth of ECSI and their contribution to the transformation of the agricultural system and the transformation of the conventional agri-businesses and their value chains. The project EdiCitNet, funded by the European Commission specifically by the European Agency for Small- and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME), seeks for innovative small-scale solutions in order to contribute to resilient cities and sustainable economic ecosystems. The huge financial crises were at that time the initial point to set up think tanks for concepts which contribute to the transformation of the conventional economic system yet the agricultural industry as part of it. Edible City Solutions thus contribute to tackling social and environmental challenges in

¹Fichter, K. & Olteanu, Y. (2021). Green Startup Monitor 2021. Berlin: Borderstep Institut, Bundesverband Deutsche Startups e.V.

² Emerson, Jed. The nature of returns: a social capital markets inquiry into elements of investment and the blended value proposition. Division of Research, Harvard Business School, 2000.

³ Fuentes, S. and Valenzuela-Garcia, H. (2019) A Crossroads for Social Entrepreneurship: Profits versus Ethics. Open Journal of Business and Management, 7, 848-860.

⁴ Outcome of several meetings with GROEN 010 and polls at the marketplace (needs and demands), discussions with ECSI in Berlin on several public events like the “Wissenstadt Berlin” and “Open Humboldt” see WP7 report

⁵ Fuentes, S. and Valenzuela-Garcia, H. (2019) A Crossroads for Social Entrepreneurship: Profits versus Ethics. Open Journal of Business and Management, 7, 848-860.

cities⁶, but have also proven to have a huge and positive impact on the economic yet social system in cities. ECSI are one tool to drive transformation in cities in general but also regarding the economic micro-system. As Edible Solutions they also provide support to the food system and thus to the agricultural transformation. The BCT will therefore support the business activities in general and also specifically tackle needs and demands from the ECSI in their respective status quo. A variety of services will lead to concrete questions and concrete answers on the basis of an ECS

Business Model Canvas. A wide range of services will be developed, from FAQs and helpdesk to monitoring the impact of the BCT's work. This will contribute to a vast pool of services provided by the EdiCitNet project and will be available under edicitnet.com beyond the project time. The Marketplace (D.6.3) plays a crucial role here as a visible and tangible online platform supporting the local and regional networks of ECSI all over the world. Together, these Deliverables form the complete offer for ECSI in EdiCitNet.

6 Säumel, Ina, Suhana E. Reddy, and Thomas Wachtel. "Edible City solutions—One step further to foster social resilience through enhanced socio-cultural ecosystem services in cities." *Sustainability* 11.4 (2019): 972.

2. ECS Business/Blended Consulting Team

Specific goals in WP6 for the ECS BCT:

- Create an online Marketplace connecting ECSI, entrepreneurs and interested externals, enabling global knowledge sharing and ECS replication.
- Provide important ECSI and interested

entrepreneurs with effective blended consultancy to improve their work either to more business-related Return on investment (ROI) and/or to socio-economic value⁷ and other e.g. value proposition development and marketing strategies.

Figure 1: Value Chain developed by Suhana Reddy, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin

In EdiCitNet, the ECS BCT skills and expertise are required to facilitate the key-activities in the project, in particular:

- * **the business/blended planning and development of the ECS businesses and initiatives including the Living Labs (FRC) and beyond.**
- * **the planning, endorsement and implementation of the Transition Pathways of the Follower Cities (FC) and beyond.**
- * **the set-up and maintenance of the ECS online Marketplace (D6.3).**

Goals and Objectives

The primary goal is to identify initiatives in the project and beyond (in FRC and FC) which are willing to and seeking actively for “blended consulting” supported by EdiCitNet. Here, it is important to keep the focus on the complete

value chain⁸ of the ECSI. This selection will provide a large portfolio of ECSI covering different “best practice” cases, each case representing a different status of maturity, a different kind of business and or social activity and a different kind of individual aim: turnover from initiative to start-up, leverage of investment and income streams, development of trade-offs/ spin-offs but also the development of social return of investment, self-stabilization of Initiative (Independency)⁹ etc.

The objectives of this action contribute to the following expected impacts of the EdiCitNet project:

1. Establishment of EU Leadership in new global NBS market.
2. New economic opportunities, new products and services.
3. Leverage of investments.
4. New local green jobs.

7 Emerson, Jed, and Mark Cabaj. "Social return on investment." (2000)..

8 Value Chain developed by Suhana E. Reddy clusters and incorporates ECSI into a ECSI value system (see also D.6.3)

9 Fichter, K. & Olteanu, Y. (2021). Green Startup Monitor 2021. Berlin: Borderstep Institut, Bundesverband Deutsche Startups e.V..

These impacts, aligned with the objectives of WP6, pave the way to integrate a broad variety of ECSI. This linkage fosters the connecting of SMEs, NGOs, initiatives and other organisations seeking support for business uptake and valorisation of their goods, activities and services and social benefit to the city dwellers.

EdiCitNet will exploit results on 3 levels:

- (1) ECSI & business in the FRC by promoting the blended development of existing and new ECSI within the Living Labs and beyond.
- (2) ECSI & business created or incubated within the Transition Pathways in FC and additional replication in other cities.
- (3) Realise blended opportunities: ECS Blended Consultancy and the Marketplace, which will be the main pillars (and potential sources of revenues) to continue EdiCitNet after the end of EC funding. (GA Exploitation)

Composition of the ECS BCT

The core team of the BCT (UBER and Nabolagshager) is multidisciplinary and multicultural. The BCT includes members of EdiCitNet WP6, WP7 and WP5 (for coordination of the indicators) under supervision of a consulting agency (Borderstep Institute). The target groups are very different ECSI covering a variety of ECS measures and activities¹⁰. These varieties we often refer to as **ECSI portfolio**. This portfolio of “ECSI cases” (ECS along the whole value chain identified in an enlarged stakeholder analysis) should serve as a good and robust selection of ECSI. The selected ECSI were partially already identified in the format EdiCitNet & friends (WP 7) and are approached via the registration of ECSI at the EdiCitNet Marketplace. The BCT members hold the necessary skills and expertise required to facilitate the key-activities in the EdiCitNet project. **Alexander Schabel** (Senior Consultant on business development at Borderstep

Institute) is employed for supervising the BCT actions, **Suhana Reddy** is a member of the coordination team and researcher in the field of stakeholder engagement and blended consultancy aiming at empowering ECSI in cities to induce and support city’s transformation towards more livable cities and **Laura Martinez Izquierdo** has studied Forest Ecology and Forest Management and is now a practitioner at the ECSI Nabolagshager.

Tasks of the BCT

The BCT supports the launch and incubates the blended activities first in FRC and FC. Beyond this, the BCT will actively involve ECSI outside the project and aims at growing the number of ECSI being supported in the 4 aforementioned goals.

Tasks of the BCT:

- Provide knowledge and consultancy for ECSI within the FRC and FC and beyond. To coordinate this action WP8 and WP7 will intensively support calls and different visibility actions with BCT (like EdiCitNet & friends) to enlarge the number of potential ECSI to be advised.
- Provide consultancy to ECSI addressed in the FC within the Transition Pathways. This support is done via the matchmaking and knowledge exchange events (see point 6: “Easy uptake with SMBC”). This knowledge exchange is also conducted in WP7 with WP3 and WP4. The matchmaking (already done at the Annual Meeting in Girona (see Report, Deliverable 1.5) foresees interlinking the cities according to their needs.
- Co-develop with the ECSI tailor-made blended development and marketing strategies following the ECS Sustainable Business Model Canvas (ECS SBMC). The ECS SBMC advances the commercial, ecological and social potential of ECS involved in the FRC.
- Provide advice and train the exploitation of the ECS SBMC, within the framework of the

¹⁰ See Value Chain in D. 6.3

local Living Lab and Transition Pathways. The BCT supports the tests of ECS in the Living Labs (T3.4), in terms of economic benefits and perspectives, as the LL plan to co-develop with ECS entrepreneur's tailor-made business development and marketing strategies.

- Help the LL in modeling and planning their exploitation activities.
- Perform plausibility checks of business plans and the joint finding of the ideal finance mix (see WP3, Task 3.1.), in particular early-stage initiatives or inexperienced entrepreneurs.
- Ensure an effective market approach with support from local key-stakeholders, such as local authorities or sponsors.
- Engage FRC and FC ECSI in further networking with cities beyond the consortium
- Coach BCT interventions in the open EdiCitNet space

More in detail, with respect to the Front-Runner cities and their Living Labs, the BCT:

- Provides consulting to the selected relevant ECSI that have also been identified in the holistic stakeholder analysis for all EdiCitNet FRC. In this context, we must point out that in the project we plan to go beyond the companies that call themselves start-up, which are very few.
- Clusters and categorizes suitable initiatives already organised in the value chain
- Guides and conceptualises all FRC and FC ECSI to their respective desired goal in the

following year and plans actions for the goal in five years from that point onwards.

With respect to the Follower cities the BCT:

- Matches and visits the guidance session (both 'on site' and online) with their selected FRC ECSI (FC ECSI will get an overview over the clusters). If possible, these will be related to a FRC, if not we have to address ECSI from boundaries to the cities;
- Conceptualises replication actions and searches for ECSI similarities.

Long-term perspective of the BCT

The BCT, which continuously optimises its services and capabilities during the project as part of an ongoing learning process, is expected to become an autonomous, innovative and sustainable ECSI service after the end of the project in the form of a self-sustaining network that will continue to support cities and communities interested in engaging in an ECS endeavor.

After the end of project cooperations with other green startup initiatives and activities will have developed. This could help the ECS initiatives to gain visibility and achieve their goals set in the business and hybrid coaching.

3. Working frame of the BCT

1. Set-up of the BCT

Main members of the BCT (reflected in Person months in GA EdiCitNet) are UBER and experts from the Borderstep Institute (subcontracted by UBER) and Nabolagshager. The BCT is also supported by Wageningen University. Here, terms of references are fixed: Regular at least 2 weekly meetings between Borderstep Institute and UBER ensure the set-up and management of the work within the BCT and the conceptualisation of the dynamically adjusted contents. Furthermore, we provide a Gantt Chart (see annex 1) and a Pert Chart to manifest a timeline and make this time frame visible within the consortium. These tools provide the schedule for tasks in the BCT and the Pert chart shows the interrelations and interlinkages to Deliverables and outcomes of the project as well as other work packages and tasks. The respective partners are involved when we are crossing the bridge to the respective involvement of the task.

2. Responsibilities and Interrelation

Within the BCT, UBER is the leading Partner. The subcontracted agency steers and reflects the developed concept and continuously advises on all formats that the ECSI tries to use within the project and beyond. The basic developed context such as the essential workshops and the brokerage event are conducted by UBER. NABOLAGHAGER is a sustainable for-profit ECSI and provides the BCT with practical perspectives and operational insights in the daily work of an ECSI. In return, these inputs flow in return back to the plans from the BCT in order to optimise the work and activities of the BCT. Several other partner SMEs within the consortium are also supporting and complementing the workshops by interviews (conducted during the data collection for D.6.2). Within the workshops UBER with support of the Subcontractor and

NABOLAGSHAGER moderates the workshops and guides the collection of data for further dissemination. Access to the different ECS initiatives is via registration forms to the Marketplace. The internal network will be used to access the various ECS initiatives within the FRC and FC. The contacts have already been established.

3. Tools & Communication

Under COVID-19 the circumstances have changed significantly. During this time all our work can only be accomplished digitally and tools like online whiteboards as well as virtual meetings are the reality. Thus, brokerage, tasks, interviews and other formats are currently held exclusively virtually. As soon as it is possible the BCT will foster real brokerage events and cluster events aimed at deepening the formation of local networks and regional cluster to shorten distances of products and services along the local value chain. Here, the BCT will closely work together with WP7 in order to interlink with formats like EdiCitNet & friends and ECS Forum. The awards will also be supported by the BCT (part of WP1) The Marketplace as an online platform is here an important space for fostering the visibility and the knowledge about other ECS worldwide. It gives an insight about the most important product or services.

Figure 2: Pert Chart BCT, EdiCitNet

The EdiCitNet webpage in general attracts people from different fields of ECS as well as the general public enabling the B2C and also B2B activities. Communication is done either

via the website and different ICT platforms like the CMT and Twitter/ Instagram. The constantly growing Marketplace and its functions and provided benefits are described in D 6.3.

Figure 3.: ECS Business Model Canvas basic tool to be adjusted to the blended consultancy

3. Methodological Approach

The methodological approach is first and foremost conceptualised for very practical use. In contrast to a Triple Bottom Layered Canvas, the ECS Canvas (based on the **Sustainable Business Model Canvas, SBMC**) is easy to access and gives applicable advice in practical workshops. An already developed question catalogue with questions tackling different aspects of the ECS BMC addresses general and specific issues of the business development. Semi-structured interviews lead to a refinement of the scope of different challenges for ECS initiatives and thus build the basis for specific needs and open space workshops.

ECSI are selected via the Marketplace but we also look for ECSI who are in turn seeking consulting. A system of prioritised needs can lead to the ECSI most urgently in need of a consultancy. The action plan then foresees the development of tailor-made business plans with the **ECS Business Model Canvas (ECS SBMC)** that address the individually defined challenges and sectors of NGOs, SMEs or other relevant initiatives and organisations involved in the FRC Living Labs and beyond. The action plan addresses entities beyond those that normally consider themselves a business or start-up. Simultaneously, we find that many initiatives that consider themselves non-profit organisations are gradually evolving into start-ups as they seek financial independence from the public sector, secure long-term staff contracts or simply find a way to continue the activities¹¹.

This ultimately leads to an EdiCitNet ECSI portfolio selection - a selection that specifically but also holistically addresses the innovative streams currently existing in a global context. This portfolio is an example, but also a

collection which can be complemented and added to. Systematically structured as a chain that is also reminiscent of a supply chain or food chain¹². This collection has also served the EdiCitNet Toolbox and supported the user-friendly and applicable decision support system from WP2.

The following steps are taken to ensure a successful framework for the project deliverable:

1. Set up of the BCT tools and communication
2. Development of a specific monitoring scheme to coordinate and align all actions undertaken in the BCT to measure the impact of WP6 and the impact of the BCT on the project and on ECSI which takes part in the blended consultancy. Suitable indicators have to be selected which show the impact of the BCT on WP6 and the ECSI which take part in the Blended Consultancy. Suitable indicators are (selection):
 - a) employee numbers (divided also by gender),
 - b) growing rate of employees within 2 years (integrated in storytelling and impact monitoring) and revenue model
 - c) history and duration of ECSI in the past
 - d) milestones in the process of being stable (turn-over point from start-up to SME of
 - e) favoured and used financing tools

On the one hand, we want to measure the leverage of the BCT's work on the selected ECSI. If WP5 develops a scheme and has already integrated these indicators in their monitoring of the Living Labs we will complement our data with WP5 and vice versa. On the other hand, we want to measure the impact of the BCT on society and the general public (outreach). For this we will closely interact with WP7 in order

¹¹ Fichter, K. & Olteanu, Y. (2021). Green Startup Monitor 2021. Berlin: Borderstep Institut, Bundesverband Deutsche Startups e.V.

¹² European Commission/Farm2ForkStrategy
/https://ec.europa.eu/food/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

to seek formats to promote our work. Even the integration of ECSI from outside the project support the outreach of the BCT activities and enrich the pool of knowledge for exchange.

3. The EdiCitNet Stakeholder List of ECSI (D.6.2) for each FRC in order to provide comparable yet different ECS categories. This is aiming at selecting a set or portfolio of ECS which provide a holistic base for replication in other cities.
4. Identify suitable parameters and categories for creating an EdiCitNet portfolio of ECS initiatives/business for the various sections service, products and valorisation of other goods and services along the whole ECS value chain.
5. Develop “Easy uptake events with “ECS SBMC”. We developed a set of knowledge sharing events and trainings on ECS SBMC to provide guidance and individual support for selected ECSI. After that we set up a portfolio of ECSI which were successfully supported and represent the different ECSI along the whole value chain (Value Chain exercise)
6. Undertake a refining of an existing knowledge sharing and workshop cascades for easy replication in Follower Cities and other cities.
7. Experiences and results will lead to adjusted training with new and additional members focusing on different parameters and different participants of the training.

Activities of the BCT

The BCT has developed four different work streams that cater to the diverse ECSI landscape. The approaches include online and offline workshops, content collection and the monitoring of impacts generated within the BCT. The four main activities are the following:

1. **ECS essential knowledge** (accompanied by an evaluation system (7 standard questions, see Annex)): A series of workshops and webinars will focus on

general aspects of how to plan and operate a successful ECSI. The webinars will feature content from experts in the field and successful ECSI and will cover a wide range of issues such as:

- a. Legal aspects of starting an ECSI: A literature review will assess the current knowledge in the field of national and European legal challenges and opportunities for ECSI in their specific status.
- b. Integration of sustainability criteria: Different status quo of sustainability rules within the ECSI as compliance for tackling/improve the all over footprint of an ECSI
- c. Basic FAQ’s will be complemented until all basic questions have been answered. Here, a small guideline and recommendation catalogue will be set up in a suitable format.

Core to direct follow-up workshops on the essential workshops are the tailor-made workshops for introducing the ECS Sustainable Business Model Canvas. The structure of these workshops will be oriented along the different canvas segments tailored to the needs of the ECSI.

2. **Brokerage events:** Based on the need’s assessment taking place on the ECS Marketplace and the essential knowledge workshops, specific brokerage events will be organized along the ECSI value chain. These events will be tailored to the needs of a group of initiatives that have common barriers to overcome. The BCT will prepare these events incorporating external and local partners. The initial needs assessment has been conducted on the basis of the Marketplace registrations and the first BCT activities. The concept at this point includes the following brokerage focus areas:
 - a. **Seed, soil and space:** Focus on challenges along the value chain of managing a successful plant growth and thus production. Here, the brokerage would exemplify the matching of

services and or products needed. The matching of needs will foster local and regional networks and thus contribute to the city's transformation.

- b. **Technologies:** Focus on the use of different ECS technologies such as light, food security, technologies for irrigation, resource- and nutrition cycles.
 - c. **Buildings:** Focus on all aspects related to the physical building infrastructure as well as the required approval procedures. This includes the development of building-related ECS such as green roofs. We have already started to develop standards on ECS and promote innovation of ECSI through sustainable technologies (see Impact V in GA)
 - d. **Digital and social engagement:** Focus on how to successfully engage with the local and online community as well as setting up a small yet integrative network and local/regional clusters for ECSI along the value chain.
3. **Specific needs and Open Space:** Based on feedback from the ECSI essential knowledge workshops and the brokerage events, the BCT will provide ECSI with tailored and case-specific support where possible. This service will be provided in the form of an open forum that can be accessed either through the EdiCitNet website, the Marketplace or by contacting the BCT team directly (contact email: edicitnet-marketplace-responds).

This open space should also enable “confidential” questions to be asked to the experts from the BCT. It is the aim of the BCT to counsel at least 5-10 ECS per calendar year in the timeframe from 2021-2023.

4. **Impact monitoring and storytelling:** On the basis of the previously described activities the BCT will identify 3-5 ECS that will be part of a thorough impact monitoring. UBER will conduct an initial interview with the founding team of these ECSI and subsequently conduct follow-up interviews as well as questionnaires on an annual basis. The aim of this activity is both

to ensure a good quality and impact of the BCT interventions as well as to provide the EdiCitNet project with interesting content used in external communication. The interviews will be semi-structured interviews including some easily applicable indicators e.g., number of employees, return of investment slope, upscaling, number of B2C and B2B.

Current status of the activities in BCT

Details of the planned activities can be seen in the Gantt chart (see Annex 1). A first ECSI essential knowledge workshop has been conducted as a virtual conference under the management of Nabolagshager in Oslo. The event with the title “Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture” took place on October 23rd and was attended by approximately 30 participants. Several specific needs were identified in this workshop which will now lead to the planning of a dedicated brokerage event in Norway. Also, some ECSI will receive specific and individual BCT support over the coming months.

The team has now also conducted two workshops in Berlin and in Koblenz. Koblenz was identified as a suitable partner for the workshops that aimed at connecting ECSI with a) experts on financing tools and b) with drivers from the economic department in both cities. Koblenz was selected after an analysis of the current state of the ECSI in this region (s. D6.2). As Andernach is part of the region Rhineland - Palatinate and most of the ECSI are located in the agglomeration area of Koblenz the BCT decided to involve the department for economic development Koblenz into the project. Andernach lacks such a department due to its small size. A small stakeholder analysis was conducted by UBER in order to identify suitable regional and local stakeholder in Berlin and Koblenz. The four key speakers were representatives of the Department for Economic Development, which are specialised in start-ups in Berlin and regional and local economic development in Koblenz. We held a

4-hour workshop with different contributions and interactive sessions.

The first item was the replicable Value Chain exercise aims to locate the ECSI within the Value Chain System for ECS. This serves as continuous training for a) identification with a novel system “the ECS” and their exploitation within an initiative or enterprise and b) a first insight into the local and regional area where the ECSI operates. The second item was an input from experts for financing and introduction of common financing tools to the ECSI. This second item was selected based on the results of the Green Start-Up Monitor 2021¹³ from Borderstep Institute. Through Borderstep we identified and recruited the experts from Crowddesk which organised an informative session on the above-mentioned topics for Berlin and Koblenz. The third item, a strategic session, was accompanied by experts

from the decision-making level from the department for economic development. These experts provided insight into different channels of support for ECSI, but also valuable information about on how to create your own start-up within the City and its administrative structures. The fourth item was an online evaluation poll, laying the base for the tailor-made workshops and the brokerage events. A total of 16 ECSI participated in both workshops. A follow-up is planned in September until December in Berlin, Koblenz, Rotterdam and Oslo.

The next steps are the cascade of workshop to develop an evidence base which also allows the adjustment of the Sustainable Business Model Canvas. UBER and Borderstep will develop a new Canvas as a supporting tool here, specifically designed for ECSI and their needs as hybrid initiatives.

¹³ Fichter, K. & Olteanu, Y. (2021). Green Startup Monitor 2021. Berlin: Borderstep Institut, Bundesverband Deutsche Startups e.V.

4. Summary

A workshop cascade, as described in section “Current status of activities”, will lead to continuous feedback and thus a knowledge pool for the Marketplace via the BCT. We aim to gather easily digestible and implementable knowledge and practical advice. ECSI in particular seem to work on a very low administrative and less theoretical base and the BCT always strives to reduce big and complicated knowledge access for ECSI. In the BCT we will adjust to the needs of these initiatives, organisations, SME as well as SEs and others in order to meet their demand for putting their energy into their “real work”. While the ECSI grows the theoretical framework by “reality checks” by the BCT in turn adjusts and digests the information and knowledge in order to fully grasp the full potential of our ECSI. The guidance in turn thrives on mutual learning and so the ECSI highly and actively support the BCT in upscaling and transferring knowledge in all local and regional networks. On the one hand their main work on business-related topics can be optimized, on the other it is necessary to gather and spread their experience. As an example of very resilient economic work and a sustainable working framework ECSI are nearly all best practice examples for the green economy and its application. With the help of ECSI all over the world these best-practices have to be visible to a broader (economic) community which will be inspired to change and transform the conventional economic structures and more specifically their value chains.

The BCT will identify the most specific and characteristic topics and issues and prepare them in such a way that they are easy to communicate and apply. The BCT will therefore actively support the aims of the Green Economy Strategy and fosters resilient cities.

Glossary

Abbreviation	Description
BCT	Business Consulting Team - a team of business consultants that foster the innovative ECS to enhance and support market uptake as well as upscaling and replication world-wide
EdiCitNet	Edible City Network
ECS SBMC	Sustainable Business Model Canvas, a variation of the common strategic business development tool developed by A. Osterwalder, which often replaces conventional business plans, extended to incorporate questions related to sustainability
3BMC	The Triple Layered Business Model Canvas, a specialized variation of the BMC into a triple bottom line model that also includes the environmental and social aspects of a business model.
ECS BMC	Edible City Solutions Business Model Canvas, a variation of the Sustainable Business Model Canvas tool based on BMC from A. Osterwalder, which will be specifying the needs of ECS.
FRC	Front Runner City
FC	Follower City
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
SE	Social Entrepreneurs
ECSI	Edible City Solution Initiatives - All Initiatives providing products and services around ECS nor matter of profit-oriented or non-profit oriented are assembled under this term

Annex 1:

Agenda Example Workshop Berlin

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 776665

AGENDA

1. Berlin Workshop "Blended Consultancy" 15. Juni 2021, 12:30 – 15:30 (CET)

Special Key-Speaker:

Niklas Marx (**CrowdDesk**),

Norbert Herrmann und Helen Franke (**Senatsverwaltung für Wirtschaft, Energie und Betriebe**)

Einwahllink (am besten über Chrome oder Firefox Browser): [ZOOM](#)

Ablaufplan

Uhrzeit	Programm	Wer
12:30-12:40	Begrüßung durch die Organisatoren: Das Blended Consultancy Team	<i>Alexander Schabel</i> (Borderstep Institut) & <i>Suhana Reddy</i> (Humboldt Universität zu Berlin) & <i>Laura Martinez Izquierdo</i> (Nabolagshager)
12:40-13:15	Vorstellungsrunde: Kennenlernen und Positionieren in der „Value chain“ (Miro board)	<i>Warum bin ich ein ECS? Und wenn ja, wie viele gibt es von mir?</i>
13:15-13:30	Finanzierungstools: Eine Einführung	<i>Ein Überblick von Alexander Schabel</i>
13:30-14:00	Erfolgreiche Projektfinanzierung	mit <i>Niklas Marx</i> von <i>CrowdDesk</i>
14:00-14:10	Diskussion und Vertiefung	Wir alle
14:15-14:45	Strategische Unterstützung für Start-ups	<i>Norbert Herrmann</i> und <i>Helen Franke</i> stellen sich und ihre Kompetenzen vor
14:45-14:55	Diskussion	Wir alle
14:55-15:25	Evaluation und Vertiefung	Wir alle
15:25-15:30	Schlusswort	Wir alle

Annex 2

Gantt Chart

About the EdiCitNet project

EdiCitNet is demonstrating innovative nature-based solutions (NBS). Edible City Solutions (ECS) are going one step further: We include the whole chain of urban food production, distribution and utilisation for inclusive urban regeneration and address societal challenges such as mass urbanisation, social inequality and climate change and resource protection in cities.

Thank you! **www: edicitnet.com**

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